

Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria

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Abstract

Using a sample of 1,120 firm year observations over the 2012-2021 period, we provide the first evidence on the impact of board of directors on dividend policy in Nigeria. Board of directors was measured by board size and board independence, while dividend policy was measured by dividend paid per share. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Method, we find that board size and board independence have significant effects on listed firms dividend policy. In Nigeria. Consistent with the agency theory and signaling hypotheses, we find that this result is more pronounced in firms with long years of experience of listing and huge size. This study points to a promising direction for future research to gain a deeper understanding of how the board of directors affects corporate policies and behaviour. However, the study is limited by the number of samples, specifically 112 listed firms. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies and also by adding to the research period or using all companies. Our study results show that the R² square value is 49.3 percent, meaning that there is room for improvement in the model of the study. Further research is expected to add other board of directors proxies that may influence the decisions made in a company such as board gender diversity, and board shares ownership.

Keywords

Board of directors, board independence/composition, board size, dividend per share, dividend policy, firm listing age, firm size, Nigeria

JEL Classification Codes

G2, G32, G34

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Journal Editor and two other reviewers for their constructive feedback on the earlier versions.

To cite this article

Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence, and dividend policy in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.

1. Introduction

Basically, finance is a management science field. The subject borders behavioural economics, sociology, economics, business, corporate governance, and accounting. It relates to several other issues, for example, the mixture of debt and interest, profit planning, the assessment of project financing options, futures, swaps, derivatives, portfolio diversification, and dividend policy. Each of these aforementioned items have been well discussed in academic circle. However, in this paper, attempt is made to focus on the role of boards of directors in influencing dividend policies of firms.

A dividend policy is the strategy a firm uses to configure its dividend payout to shareholders. Some researchers suggest the dividend policy is irrelevant, in theory, because shareholders can sell their shares if they need funds. This perspective is called the dividend irrelevance theory. It simply states that dividend payouts minimally affect a share's price. However, despite the theory that dividend policy is irrelevant, it is income for shareholders. Directors are often the largest shareholders and have the most to gain from a generous dividend policy.

Most companies view a dividend policy as an integral part of their corporate strategy. By implications, management must decide on the dividend amount, timing, and various other factors that influence dividend payments. Dividend policy of a firm has been hotly discussed among scholars (Abor & Bokpin, 2010; Adaoglu, 2000; Allen & Michaely, 1995; Al-Malkawi et al., 2010; Amidu, 2007; Belda-Ruiz et al., 2022; Ben-Salah & Ben-Amar, 2022; DeAngelo & DeAngelo, 1990; Dickens et al., 2020; Fama & Blahnik, 1968; Farinha, 2003; Frankfurter & Wood Jr, 2002; Grassetti et al., 2023; Hasan et al., 2023; Jiraporn et al., 2011; Leary & Michaely, 2011; Mancinelli & Ozkan, 2006; Mehta, 2012; Neugebauer et al., 2023; Shao et al., 2010; Sheikh et al., 2022; Tinungki et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2023; Zainudin et al., 2018).

Some scholars have linked it with the role of corporate governance in enhancing dividend policy (Arena & Julio, 2023; Bakri et al., 2021; Boshnak, 2021; Dunham et al., 2023; Farooque, et al., 2021; Fayyaz et al., 2023; Hartono et al., 2021; Hossain et al., 2023; Mubaraq et al., 2021; Nazar, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2021; Waris et al., 2021; Widyasti & Putri, 2021; Yahaya, 2022; Yilmaz et al., 2022).

Others have discussed it more commonly with the ownership structure of a firm (Bataneh, 2021; Hasan et al., 2023; Khan, 2022; Ko & Joh, 2009; Kong et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2023; Tnushi et al., 2022; Yilmaz et al., 2022). Some others have associated it with the firm financial performance or profitability (Abdullah, 2021; Bilyay-Erdogan et al., 2023; Jovković et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2021; Sholichah et al., 2021; Wau, 2021; Widyasti & Putri, 2021; Yahaya, 2017).

However, very little research works have been carried out in order to establish how much influence could the board of directors brings to the table in shaping a firm's dividend policy. This is the objective of this article, that is, to show the influence of board of directors on dividend policy of firms in Nigeria. Dividend policy of a firm is often seen from four different perspectives: dividend to asset, dividend per share, dividend yield, and dividend payout. However, in this study, dividend policy is measured by dividend paid per share, which

accounts for more than an absolute value. It accounts for the dividend paid out, as well as the amount of equity shares outstanding at the end of every financial year.

The board of directors is the highest decision making structure in any business organisation. It makes common term decisions regarding direction of development of commerce of the firm and supervises its overall operations. Thus, the managerial capacity of the board of directors is of critical importance for the operation of the business firm and for accomplishment of its general mission and objectives. For effective and clear running of the board of directors, it has been proposed by the Nigerian Governance Code 2018 that the number of individual non-executive directors be more than the executive directors in order to guaranty independence. Furthermore, the Code addresses the minimum number of directors in a firm's board as 8 members. In view of these guidelines, this article looks at board of directors from two perspectives: board size and board independence.

Board size has been popularly researched by scholars (Ahmed et al., 2006; Bennedsen et al., 2008; Conyon & Peck, 1998; Di Pietra et al., 2008; Dwivedi & Jain, 2005; Goodstein et al., 1994; Huther, 1997; Kumar & Singh, 2013; Rouf & Hossan, 2021; Tanna et al., 2011; Uwuigbe & Fakile, 2012). However, few empirical studies have related board size with the dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. It is for this reason including others earlier explained that this article discusses the role of board size in dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria.

Board independence, also known as board composition has well been discussed in empirical literature by scholars (Ahmed et al., 2006; Alves, 2014; Ararat et al., 2010; Bhagat & Black, 2001; Cheng et al., 2022; Gani & Jermias, 2006; Goh et al., 2016; Kumar & Sivaramakrishnan, 2008; Rosenstein & Wyatt, 1990; Rouf & Hossan, 2021; Rutledge et al., 2016; Tanna et al., 2011; Zaid et al., 2020). However, few empirical studies have related board size with the dividend policy of a firm in Nigeria. It is for this reason including others earlier explained that this article discusses the role of board independence in dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. The remaining part of this article is devoted to literature review, methodology, results, discussion, conclusion, recommendations, and references.

2. Literature Review

This articles relies heavily on two theories: agency and signaling theory. Agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), which states that a firm's board of directors is an agent for shareholders, acting for their own interests not as a party that sided with the shareholders as assumed in the stewardship model. Agency theory explains that board of directors cannot be trusted to act in the best way for the shareholders. Thus, directors, simply executive directors cannot be trusted to do their jobs - which of course is to maximize shareholder value. In these words, the board of directors is a core part of corporate governance structure. This article is based on the agency conflict arising the clash of interests of directors and shareholders. The agents are the directors and the shareholders are the principals. Agency theory tries to offer clearance over conflict between the agent and principal.

Signaling theory is a theory that firm insiders have more information about their firm's financial health than outside parties, and that they can reveal this information through their decisions. These decisions can take various forms, such as dividends, stock buybacks, debt issuances, or voluntary disclosures. These signals are intended to change the valuation of the company by the market or the stakeholders. Signaling theory is one of the pillar theories in understanding financial management and financial communications policy. Signaling theory predicts a relationship between board characteristics and dividend policy, as board members may have more incentive to signal higher dividends.

In terms of empirical studies, Farinha (2003) analyses the agency explanation for the cross-sectional variation of corporate dividend policy in the UK and find firm size to have significant influence on dividend policy. Also, Hu and Kumar (2004) develop and test a novel perspective on payout policy that integrates the influence of internal governance mechanisms. Their model performs well in both in-sample and out-of-sample predictions on a sample of 2,081 firms during 1992–2000. They find both board independence and firm age to have significant effects on dividend policy. Furthermore, Chen et al. (2005) analyze a sample of 412 publicly listed Hong Kong firms during 1995–1998 in order to answer the question if corporate governance and dividend payouts are related? They conclude that the composition of the board of directors (proportion of independent non-executive directors, outsider-dominated boards) has little impact on firm performance and dividend policy in Hong Kong.

Abdelsalam et al. (2008) examine dividend policies in an emerging capital market, in a country undergoing a transitional period using pooled cross-sectional observations data from the top 50 listed Egyptian firms between 2003 and 2005. It is found that there is no significant association was found between board composition and dividend decisions or ratios. Furthermore, Sulong and Nor (2008) examine the effects of dividends on board governance in Malaysia using a sample of 406 listed firms on the Main Board of Bursa Malaysia over a cross-sectional analysis for the years 2002 and 2005. Results show that the interaction between dividends and board independence was positively significant. Whereas, the interaction between dividends and board size showed significantly lower coefficient positive.

Al-Najjar and Hussainey (2009) examine whether the number of outside directors (board independence) on the board of directors and dividend payout are substitutes or complements mechanisms applied by UK firms to control agency conflicts of interest within the firm. Based on a sample of 400 non-financial firms listed at London Stock Exchange for the period from 1991 to 2002, it was found that dividend payout is negatively associated with the number of outside directors on the board of directors. The study also find that firm size has significant effect on dividend policy. Furthermore, Bokpin and Arko (2009) examine the effect of corporate governance on dividend decisions of firms on the Ghana Stock Exchange using unbalanced panel data covering a period from 2002 to 2007 is employed using the seemingly unrelated regression approach. Among the corporate governance variables, board size is found to be positively and statistically significantly related to dividend choices.

Setia-Atmaja (2010) examines whether board independence influences dividend policies of family controlled firms. The paper examines panel data on a sample of Australian publicly-listed firms over the period 2000-2005 using panel (random effects) regression. The result indicates that the positive impact of family control on dividend policy is due to the higher proportion of independent directors on family boards. Also, Al-Shabibi and Ramesh (2011) examine the factors which affect dividend policy for 90 nonfinancial UK companies in the year 2007. In particular, the research examines the extent to which corporate governance factors affect corporate dividend policy. It was reported by the study that board size has no significant effect on dividend policy. However, it was reported in the same study that board independence and firm size have significant effects on dividend policy.

Similarly, in 2011, Jiraporn et al. investigate how a firm's overall quality of corporate governance affects its dividend policy using a large sample of firms with governance data from The Institutional Shareholder Services, they find that firms with stronger board independence exhibit a higher propensity to pay dividends. The study also find firm size to have significant influence on dividend policy. Also, Sharma (2011) uses data from 944 public companies in 2006, to examine how a firm's propensity to pay dividends is related to board independence and find evidence of a positive association between the propensity to pay and board independence. Furthermore, Bokpin (2011) documents the interaction between ownership structure, corporate governance and dividend performance on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE). Panel data covering a period from 2002 to 2007 for 23 firms were analyzed within the framework of fixed effects techniques. Results show that board size has a statistically positive effect on dividend payment among the corporate governance variables. It did not, however, find a significant relationship between board independence and dividends.

Uwuigbe (2013) investigates the determinants of dividends policy in the Nigerian stock exchange market using a sample of 50 listed firms in the Nigerian stock exchange market. Annual reports for the period 2006-2011 were used for the study. The study in its findings observed that there is a significant positive relationship between size of firms and board independence on the dividend payouts decisions of listed firms in Nigeria. Also, Abor and Fiador (2013) examine the effect of corporate governance on firms' dividend payout policy in sub-Saharan Africa using a sample made up 27 Ghanaian firms, 177 Nigerian firms, 51 Kenyan firms, and 270 South African firms covering the period 1997-2006. The results show that board composition (independence) and board size exhibit significantly positive relationship with dividend payout in Kenya and Ghana, respectively. In the case of Nigeria, the two corporate governance measures show significantly negative effects on dividend payout.

Nuhu (2014) re-examines the factors that determine dividend payout in Ghana. The sample for the study was drawn from 30 listed firms on the Ghana Stock Exchange from 2000 to 2009. The study used ordinary least squares panel regression model to estimate the determinants of dividend payout. The results show that board size and board independence are important determinants of dividend payout in Ghana.

McGuinness et al. (2015) examine the association between Chinese stock issuers' board characteristics and dividends. They focus on the board demographics and characteristics using more than 9,000 firm-year observations. The result shows that the proportion of independent directors on boards bears association with cash pay-out. Also, Roy (2015) investigates the possible association between the firm's ownership structure and dividend policy and whether the corporate governance (CG) practices adopted by the firm have any impact on dividend policy. They use a panel of 51 top Indian listed firms, in terms of market capitalisation (BSE 100 and NIFTY 100), over the 5-year period from 2007–2008 to 2011–2012. They conclude that the CG variables, namely, board size, independent directors and the proportion of non-executive directors on the board have significant impact on the dividend policy of the firm. Furthermore, Yarram and Dollery (2015) examine the influence of board structure on dividend policy of Australian corporate firms using a sample, which consists of 413 non-financial firms that are part of the All Ordinaries Index for the study period 2004-2009. This study finds that board independence has a significant positive influence on the dividend payout of Australian firms. Also, this study finds that firm size has a significant positive influence on the dividend payout of Australian firms.

Benjamin et al. (2016) investigate the effects of family ownership on dividend payout from the perspective of agency costs in Malaysia. Annual financial, board and family ownership data of 160 firms listed on the Bursa Malaysia are collected for the period 2005-2010. The empirical results suggest that firm size and dividend policy are significantly correlated. Also, Khan and Ahmad (2017) determine the impact of profitability, growth opportunities, risk, liquidity, firm size, leverage, taxation and audit type on dividend payout within Pakistani corporate environment using five year financial data from 2009-2014 of listed pharmaceutical companies. Firm size insignificantly influences dividend payout decisions of pharmaceutical companies.

In addition, Mehdi et al. (2017) study the impact of the ownership structure and board governance on dividend policy in emerging markets using a panel regression approach on a sample of 362 non-financial listed firms from East Asian and Gulf Cooperation Council countries. It is shown that board independency affects significantly the dividend policy of firms. Finally, the results show that dividend decision is inversely related to board size. Also, Elmagrhi et al. (2017) examine the extent to which corporate board characteristics influence the level of dividend pay-out ratio using a sample of UK small- and medium-sized enterprises from 2010 to 2013 listed on the Alternative Investment Market. The data are analysed by employing multivariate regression techniques, including estimating fixed effects, lagged effects and two-stage least squares regressions. The results show that board size has a significant relationship with the level of dividend pay-out. By contrast, the findings suggest that board independence does not have any significant effect on the level of dividend pay-out.

In 2018, Subramaniam investigates the relationship between family ownership and dividend in Malaysian publicly listed firms using data from 712 firms over the period of five (5) years from the year 2010 to 2014. Adjusted ordinary least square (OLS) regression methods are employed to analyse the data used in the study. Based on the results, board size has no significant influence on dividend policy. However, firm size had significant effect on dividend

policy. Also, Rajput and Jhunjhunwala (2019) study the impact of ownership structure and corporate governance on dividend policy in emerging markets, like India. The data set of 1,546 Indian firms over the period of 2006-2017 has been used in this study. First, the study finds a significant positive influence of corporate governance on the decision to pay dividend. Finally, the result from the interaction effect of board independence has significant positive influence on dividend policy. Furthermore, Tahir et al. (2020) examine the extent to which corporate board attributes influence dividend payout policies. A total number of 2,842 firm's year-observations of Malaysian non-financial firms representing various industries. The firms were scrutinized over a period of 14 financial years covering from 2005 to 2018. The results revealed that board independence and board size have positive and statistically mixed effects on dividend pay-out.

Khan (2021) investigates the impact of ownership structure and board characteristics on dividend policy in the listed Turkish firms between 2013 and 2019 using panel data set drawn from the Borsa Istanbul (BIST) 100 index, excluding financial and utility firms. The empirical findings indicate that board size is positive and significant. Additionally, board independence is insignificant in influencing firms to pay high dividends. Furthermore, Thompson and Manu (2021) examine whether the characteristics of boards are more important in determining dividend policy using the dividend declaration dummy variable, the authors run a fixed effect logistic regression. The results of the study show that board characteristics such as board size has a strong positive significant effect.

Abu-Afifa et al. (2022) examine the nexus between board characteristics and dividend payout. The study population consists of all service firms that were listed on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) between 2012 and 2019. Panel data analysis was employed. Based on the GMM estimator findings, the findings found that board size had a significant negative effect on dividend payout, while board independence did not. Furthermore, Ellili (2022) examines the nexus between environmental, social, and governance (ESG) disclosure and dividend policy by considering the major role of corporate governance. The sample consists of companies traded in the UAE financial markets during the period 2010–2020. The results reveal that board of directors' independence is a mediator in the relationship between ESG disclosure and dividend payout. Also, Kanojia and Bhatia (2022) examine the relationship between corporate governance and dividend payout, using a sample of Indian and US listed firms. The results show that board independence and board size are the key corporate governance drivers of dividend payout in US firms, while none of the individual corporate governance parameters is significantly associated to dividend payout in for Indian firms.

Fayyaz et al. (2023) investigate the influence of corporate governance quality on the dividend policy of Asian emerging markets. First, they assess the level of corporate governance quality through a comprehensive index comprised of the combined board governance attributes (board size and independence. Then, using a sample of non-financial firms from the stock exchanges of the respective emerging markets (China, India, and Pakistan), their results depict firms' corporate governance quality as a relevant factor for dividend pay-out. Based on the results of these empirical studies, this study hypothesizes that:
H₁: Board size has no significant effect on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria
H₂: Board independence has no significant effect on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria

3. Methodology

The final sample consists of 112 listed firms that are part of the Nigerian Exchange. The causal analysis was undertaken using the OLS regression method. The model of the study is formulated as follows:

$$DP_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BS_{i,t} + \beta_2 BI_{i,t} + \beta_3 FLA_{i,t} + \beta_4 FSIZ_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

DP = Dividend policy, measured by measured as cash dividend paid divided by numbers of shares.

BS – Board size, measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary.

BI = Board independence, measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%).

FLA = Firm listing age, measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.

FSIZ = Firm size, measured as natural log of total asset.

α = Constant

β_{1-4} = Beta coefficients

i = Firm script (i = 112 firms)

t = Time script (t = 10 years)

The data were hand-picked from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms and analysed using both descriptive (number of observations, mean, standard deviation, minimum mean, and maximum mean) and inferential statistics (coefficients, standard errors, t-value and p-value). They were also diagnosed of normality and homoscedasticity of residuals, multicollinearity, and panel effects before the choice of final regression analysis technique. The decision accept or reject criterion is based on 1%, 5% and 10% level of significance.

4. Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics describe, show, and summarize the basic features of a dataset in a given study. It is presented in a summary that describes the data sample and its measurements. It helps analysts to understand the data better. For these reasons, Table 1 shows the results of descriptive analysis of the study variables.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DP	1120	.446	.591	0	2.83
BS	1120	13.739	3.174	5	21
BI	1120	58.67	12.385	21.43	90
FLA	1120	22.693	15.512	2	50
FSIZ	1120	8.958	.463	8.03	10.77

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 1, the number of observations is 1,120, which is obtained from the number of years covered by the study (10 years) multiplied by the number of firms (112 firms). Also, dividend policy (DP) averages .446, while it has a standard deviation of .591, which is higher, suggesting that dividend paid per share is volatile and deserves to be researched. The minimum and maximum means are 0 and 2.83, respectively.

Furthermore, board size averages 14 members, while it has a standard deviation of 3 members. The minimum and maximum means are 5 and 21, respectively. In view of the Nigerian Corporate Governance Codes rule of minimum of 8 board size, it is recommended that firms with less than 8 board members should increase to at least 8 members. Also, board independence averages 58.67 percent, while it has a standard deviation of 12 percent. The minimum and maximum means are 21 and 90 percent, respectively. These results are in line with the Nigerian Corporate Governance Codes 2018, which requires that the proportion of independent non-executive directors should be higher. On the two control variables used in this paper, firm listing age averages 23 years, while it has a standard deviation of 16 years. The minimum and maximum means are 2 and 50 years, respectively. Finally, firm size (FSIZ) averages 8.958, while it has a standard deviation of .463. The minimum and maximum means are 8.03 and 10.77, respectively.

Additionally, we estimate the bi-correlation between the variables. Correlation analysis, also known as bivariate, is primarily concerned with finding out whether a relationship exists between variables and then determining the magnitude and action of that relationship. Based on this, the results are reported in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2

Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) DP	1.000				
(2) BS	0.043 (0.594)	1.000			
(3) BI	-0.220* (0.006)	-0.288* (0.000)	1.000		
(4) FLA	-0.103 (0.207)	0.142* (0.079)	-0.015 (0.851)	1.000	
(5) FSIZ	0.601* (0.000)	0.277* (0.001)	-0.080 (0.327)	0.273* (0.001)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Following from the results of correlation matrix in Table 2, board size and firm listing age are not significantly related to dividend policy. However, board independence and firm size were found to be significantly correlated with dividend policy. Furthermore, board size and board independence are correlated significantly. Also, board size and firm listing age are significantly correlated. Additionally, board size and firm size are significantly correlated.

Finally, firm size and firm listing age are significantly correlated. However, it is important to note that there are differences between correlation and regression and therefore, there is need to avoid confusion.

We also carried out series of diagnostics in order to correctly the right data analysis technique. Diagnostic analytics is the process of using data to determine the causes of trends and correlations between variables. It can be viewed as a logical next step after using descriptive analytics to identify trends. The results of these tests are reported in Table 3 as follows:

Table 3
Results of Diagnostic Tests

Serial	Test	Value
1	Normality of Residuals	.200
2	Homoscedasticity of Residuals	.411
3	Model Specification Error (ovtest)	.212
4	Multicollinearity (Mean VIF)	2.22
5	Panel Effects	.153

STATA 16 Outputs

The results in Table 3 show absence of normality and homoscedasticity of residuals. Also, there is no evidence in the results to support existence of model specification errors. Furthermore, there is no correlation among the independent and control variables as the mean variance inflation factor is less than 10. In addition, the results of the panel effects test show that there is no panel effects in the data set and therefore, the study pooled the data together and used Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS) analysis technique.

Furthermore, we carried out an OLS based regression analysis. Regression analysis involves identifying the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. A model of the relationship is hypothesized, and estimates of the parameter values are used to develop an estimated regression equation. The results of the regression analysis are reported in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4
Regression analysis

DP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val	p-val	[95% Co	Interval]	Sig
BS	-.033	.012	-2.77	.006	-.056	-.009	***
BI	-.01	.003	-3.57	.000	-.016	-.005	***
FLA	-.01	.002	-4.49	.000	-.015	-.006	***
FSIZ	.903	.08	11.25	.000	.744	1.062	***
Constant	-6.343	.72	-8.81	.000	-7.765	-4.921	***
R-squared		0.493	Number of obs		1120		
F-test		35.974	Prob > F		0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)		178.551	Bayesian crit. (BIC)		193.703		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

STATA 16 Outputs

Following from the results in Table 4, both board size and board independence show significant effects on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. Our results for Nigeria are in line with the works of some scholars (Abor & Fiador, 2013; Abu-Afifa et al., 2022; Al-Najjar & Hussainey, 2009; Al-Shabibi & Ramesh, 2011; Bokpin 2011; Bokpin & Arko, 2009; Ellili, 2022; Elmarghi et al., 2017; Fayyaz et al., 2023; Hu & Kumar, 2004; Jiraporn et al., 2011; Kanojia & Bhatia, 2022; Khan, 2020; McGuinness et al., 2019; Mehdi et al., 2017; Nuhu, 2014; Rajput & Jhunjhunwaha, 2019; Roy, 2015; Setia-Atmaja, 2010; Sharma, 2011; Sulong & Nor, 2008; Tahir et al., 2020; Thompson & Manu, 2021; Uwuigbe, 2013; Yarram & Dollery, 2015). The results confirm the major role of board size and independence in corporate governance. Furthermore, on the control variables used, both firm listing age and firm size show significant influences on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. These results are consistent with the results of some scholars (Farinha, 2003; Hu & Kumar, 2004).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has examined the effects of board and board independence on the dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. In the process, it has found board size as a determinant of dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. Also, it has found board independence as a determinant of dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. Similarly, it has also found both firm listing age and firm size as determinants of dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria. The study used both descriptive and inferential analyses to analyse the data. The two hypotheses, which state that both board size and independence have no significant effects on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria are hereby rejected and the alternate hypotheses, which state that board size and board independence have significant effects on dividend policy of listed firms in Nigeria are hereby accepted. Our results are important as they show that corporate governance does have impacts on critical corporate decisions such as dividend policy.

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